

Repositioning Individuals for Reading Competence: A Key Focus of the Smart Green Schools Initiative of Enugu State Government, Nigeria

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Abstract: This paper extols the Smart School initiative of the Enugu State government and the ultimate plan to launch the schools into the 4th industrial revolution. It points out that reading should occupy a pivotal place in the smart school curriculum. Reading involves an interaction between the reader and the printed text. That is to say that reading entails looking at the printed text to make meaning out of it. The journey of ‘learning to read’ begins in the basic or primary schools. The goal of reading instruction at the primary level is that every child should be functionally literate, able to communicate well, read and write with clear understanding, and utilize efficient problem-solving life skills. So, a solid foundation must be laid for reading competence among the pupils of the smart schools to equip them for the demands and tasks of the 4th Industrial Revolution. This is because reading failure in the past has led to educational failure as well as general underdevelopment. This paper therefore argues that from the commencement of the smart schools, adequate attention must be paid to reading instruction, quality of personnel involved, processes of delivery, and product to reposition the individuals for higher reading achievement.

Keywords: Repositioning, reading competence, initiative, smart green school

Introduction

Reading is a very fundamental language skill that is concerned with extracting meaning out of texts, be they books, printed works, or digital materials. Reading is very important and basic as a literacy tool and a means of communication and it has become an identity or a mark for identifying a literate person among others. This explains why some illiterates clutch newspapers and magazines, sometimes upside down, in the bid to convince people that they can read. Reading involves the ability to read and comprehend written texts effectively. At the school, the development of a formidable in reading achievement and reading culture, is essential not only for communication and academic purposes, but also for acquiring new competencies and enlightened citizenship//including decoding, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension (National Reading Panel, 2000). Reading competence is a critical aspect of academic success, as it enables students to access and process information across various subjects. Reading is an interactive process that goes on between the reader and the text, resulting in comprehension.

Concept of Reading

Reading is concerned with the meaning and the ability of the individual to extract meaning out of the text. The text presents letters, words, sentences and paragraphs that encode meaning. The child begins by ‘learning to read’ and graduates to ‘reading to learn.’ At this stage the child is now equipped with the tool to grow into a well informed and well developed citizen. It is also important to note that reading is the language tool that learners

will use to navigate their way throughout their educational and life journeys. It is also worthy of note that the quality of the educational attainment at higher levels is a reflection of the foundation laid at the basic levels. High reading competence therefore becomes imperative in the course of study of our children. Thus, the need to reposition learners for reading competence in the Smart Green Schools of Enugu State Government.

Reading is a multifaceted cognitive process involving at the first instance, the decoding of symbols to derive meaning. Thus, 'To learn to read' is the first level of learning reading. It is not merely the recognition of words alone that constitutes reading, but the comprehension and interpretation of text(s). This encompasses various cognitive, linguistic, and social dimensions. Reading is foundational to literacy, playing a critical role in education and personal development. It is the pathway to knowledge (Ene 2016). At this level, it is 'reading to learn' which implies now a resource that facilitates the learning of other activities in higher institutions and even out of school. In the Nigerian context, the concept of reading is deeply intertwined with the country's educational and linguistic landscape. English, introduced during the colonial era, has become the primary language of instruction in schools. The reason may not be farfetched. Nigeria's linguistic diversity, with over 400 indigenous languages, poses unique challenges in language instruction. English became a unifying language even as a second language. The change in status has various implications for the teachers and learners. Reading instruction particularly has since been very problematic due to several reasons. One of the key variables in understanding the problems of reading instruction is Nigeria's linguistic diversity. Pupils often enter school speaking one or more indigenous languages, and their transition to reading in English requires effective pedagogical strategies. This bilingual or multilingual context necessitates a nuanced approach to reading instruction, emphasizing the importance of developing proficiency in both indigenous languages and English.

Another critical variable is educational infrastructure. In many rural areas, schools lack adequate resources such as textbooks, libraries, and trained teachers, which hamper the development of reading skills. Urban schools tend to be better equipped, reflecting disparities in educational quality and access. These infrastructural challenges highlight the need for targeted interventions to bridge the gap between rural and urban educational locations (Omeje & Ugwu, 2019).

Socio-economic factors also play a significant role in shaping reading habits and proficiency. Poverty, parental education levels, and access to educational materials significantly influence students' reading abilities. In lower-income households, children may have limited exposure to books and other reading materials, which can impede their literacy development. Addressing these socioeconomic disparities is crucial for fostering a culture of reading across all strata of society (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Technological advancements present both opportunities and challenges for reading in Nigeria. The rise of digital media has transformed traditional reading practices, offering new platforms such as e-books and online articles. However, the digital divide remains a significant barrier, with limited access to technology in rural areas. Integrating digital literacy into the educational curriculum can enhance reading skills, but it requires substantial investments in technology and training (Adegbite, 2016).

Cultural factors are also equally important in understanding reading practices in Nigeria. The oral tradition remains strong, with storytelling and verbal communication playing a vital role in cultural transmission. While this rich oral heritage is an asset, it can sometimes compete with the development of reading habits. Educational initiatives must therefore balance the promotion of reading with the preservation of cultural practices (Igboanus & Peter, 2019). As it is, the problem of reading in Nigeria is multi-faceted. If it is not lacking the opportunity to

learn to read, it is reading without understanding, not being taught reading well enough, or not interested in reading.

Why Repositioning

The high rate of reading failure among primary school leavers has been a source of concern to all stakeholders in the education system. This concern stems from the fact that any reading failure at the basic level has huge implications for the entire tiers of the education system. Sometimes, it manifests as ‘Reluctant Reading and Learning Syndrome’ (Unoh in Akaegbobi 2014). Besides, baseline reports show that Nigeria is only at a 26% reading rate (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). This shows that literacy is very low, especially in some Northern states like Zamfara, and Jigawa Kebbi. Insecurity has even compounded the matter of educational access. According to a World Bank report of 2022, only 15% of Nigerians have completed Primary education. In some states, many Nigerians cannot even identify their names where they are written, cannot read directions or road signs, and cannot even understand or interpret things like pay slips, receipts, or change. (UNESCO 2020). Another matter of concern is that many of those who managed to get up to First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC), quickly slide back to illiteracy once they are out of school (Omojuwa as cited in Akaegbobi, 2014).

The idea of re-positioning means that there must be flaws in the erstwhile approaches to teaching reading, which necessitates a paradigm shift. For the Smart Green Schools, English language and reading pedagogy in particular, must be critically reviewed to sharpen it so that reading must take a pride of place in the Smart Green Schools of Enugu State. Thus, in relation to the Smart School initiative which promises to revolutionise the education system, especially at the grassroots, then there is every need to ensure repositioning of the individual for higher reading achievement even as the Smart schools take off in Enugu state.

Reading failures may be traceable to factors relating to schools and their curriculum. Let us consider the following factors:

- i. Quality of Teachers/Competence.
- ii. Dearth of teachers.
- iii. Reading Pedagogy Issues.

Quality of Teachers/ Competence

Teachers’ competence is key to the provision of effective reading instructions for pupils in the primary schools. Teachers need to have the right skills and competencies of how to package and present reading instructions in the best way to make pupils learn reading successfully. The National Policy on Education (FGN 2014) states that the minimum qualification for teaching at the basic level in Nigeria is the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE). But there still seems to be untrained and un-certificated teachers in the school system, leading to a steady decline in the quality of the teachers in the system. (Omojuwa in Akaegbobi, 2014) This situation contributes to the diminishing of the pupils’ language ability in general and reading in particular. There are still untrained teachers in some of our schools and even the trained ones are poorly prepared to teach reading. They are deficient in essential knowledge, skills and abilities required for reading instruction especially in a bilingual or multilingual context. The content of the teacher preparation programs for primary school teachers are too superficial and general and therefor lacking in depth. This renders them deficient for the basic principles and skills involved for effective reading instruction for bilingual children. As Akaegbobi, (2014) clearly put it, ‘Those assigned to teach reading in our nursery and elementary schools were never taught reading and are not aware that reading is a sophisticated discipline that cannot be handled by those who are not aware of what it is’

Dearth of Teachers

Despite the enormous turn of teachers during the Universal Primary Education programme (UPE, 1975) and UBE programme (Universal Basic Education of (1999), there is still a dearth of teachers in our school system. Many schools still employ auxiliary teachers, National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) members and Community teachers Ene, (2018). In some cases, the Head teacher of short staffed schools simply assigns any available person to teach English Language to pupils. This is unfortunate, to say the least. It has been noted that untrained teachers are simply ‘cheats of the system’ (Ene, 2018). Such teachers have done more harm than good. It becomes a tragedy when people who themselves were not even well taught are now teaching English to second Language learners. What do they know about language learning not to talk about the processes of teaching reading, which is critical to the success of the education system?

Reading Pedagogy Issues

Another problem militating against reading achievement in primary schools is methods of reading instruction. Teaching methods play a crucial role in reading achievement. Many children have failed to read mostly because of poor teaching methods. Many methods are actually available. There is a process of teaching starters who are ‘learning to read’ This involves the reading readiness stage of preparation, the Alphabetic method, the Phonic method, letter formation method, simple sentences formation methods. Only well trained and experienced teachers can handle teaching English at this stage. Further training is given to teachers on ‘Jolly Phonics’ to encourage them to practice the rudiments of proper phonetics and phonology. Jolly phonics is a British Council program designed to enhance the reading process, sound articulation, stress and intonation.

This lays the foundation for children’s reading interest and paves the way for children to get hooked on to reading. When children have learnt to read, they come to the next level of ‘Reading to Learn’. They must be encouraged by parents and schools to providing them enough books, as appropriate, to help them practice. Support must come from homes as well as schools. Again children are taught to use the library. It must not be only school library. Teachers can create class library or reading corners or mobile library. Reading corners are created and children are encouraged to read there during break or library time (if the provision is made in the timetable. As time goes on, the children become hooked on reading because they find it very enjoyable even more than watching films or eating food or sleeping.. Students soon become more inquisitive to read everything they see everywhere, whether in the bus, in the car, in the train, on a travel, in a flight, in the bedroom, in the toilet, everywhere.

With this they develop the reading culture and now begin to do what Okoye (2011) says ‘Read something everywhere’? In Nigeria if you talk about paying special attention to reading, you will be challenged by so many antagonists who feel that English language is dominating other indigenous languages. But the fact remains that English is the language of instruction and failure in English language leads to failure in the entire education system Omojuwa in Akaegbobi, 2014). Besides English has become a global language with high economic value. So we are better off using English for our national and international interactions and it will positively affect our literacy and human development index (HDI).

Way Forward

The researcher considers the following: Modern methods of teaching second language readers, Teacher professional development, Reading initiatives and programmes, and the influence of media. In relation to modern language teaching, there are things that your grandmother’s teacher didn’t know, that your granddaughter’s teacher should know. This is because things are changing fast. The goals of reading instruction at the primary

level is that every child should be functionally literate, able to communicate well, read and write with clear understanding, utilize efficiently problem solving life skills. The Smart Schools should apply tech tools and tech skills. Multimedia platforms, visual and audio visual tools, immersion techniques, smart classroom techniques, language applications, modern language laboratories and classrooms etc. These will enhance the opportunity to lay a solid foundation for reading competence among the pupils of the smart schools. This will help to equip them for the demands and tasks of the 4th Industrial revolution.

The high rate of reading failure especially among primary school leavers has bedevilled the Nigerian education system. Reading researches point to the fact that there is a relationship between language success and academic success. The particular language skill involved is reading because it has to do with meaning and comprehension and even children's general attitude to study and learning. According to Omojuwa in Akaegbobi, (2014), it was discovered that pupils at the completion of primary schools(First School Leaving Certificate) are still at the basic level of literacy judging by their reading competency.

Teacher professional development (TPD) is a cornerstone of effective reading instruction. Continuous training and professional development opportunities enable teachers to stay abreast of the latest research and instructional techniques. In Nigeria, expanding access to professional development for teachers, particularly in rural areas, is crucial for improving the quality of reading education (Ene, 2021). Reading initiatives and programs spearheaded by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international agencies have also contributed to literacy development in Nigeria. Programs that provide books, train teachers, and create reading-friendly environments have shown positive impacts. Collaboration between government, NGOs, and communities can amplify these efforts and create sustainable change (Adegbite, 2016).

The influence of media on reading practices is an emerging area of interest. Television, radio, and social media can be harnessed to promote literacy and encourage reading. Educational programs, broadcast in local languages and English can reach a wide audience and support literacy development. Media campaigns that highlight the importance of reading can also change societal attitudes and motivate individuals to engage with reading (Igboanusi & Peter, 2019). The concept of reading in Nigeria is a complex and dynamic interplay of linguistic, socio-economic, cultural, and technological factors.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Reading needs special attention in the smart schools of Enugu. Reading is occupying a critical position in the education system where English is a language of instruction and English is also a world language. A failure in English is a failure of the education system. But if we take the necessary steps to start children off well in reading, the problems encountered later in higher schools will be minimized. In addition, today's children are in a world of rapidly changing technologies, with Artificial Intelligence, mechatronics, and super cyber systems. The implication is high literacy demands. The children of the smart schools must have competent English and reading teachers to help them develop the essential literacy to cope with the literacy challenges of the 4th Industrial Revolution.

Based on the findings therefore, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The Enugu State government must be intentional in repositioning the reading for the benefit of smart schools
2. The government must ensure that only qualified and experienced teachers of English will man the Smart schools right from the beginning

3. Recommendation of supplementary books should be done by trained educationists
4. Enough books and other digital reading materials should be provided for the schools

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